

INTERACTIVE TEACHING METHODS AND GAMIFICATION IN DEVELOPING TECHNICAL THINKING IN STUDENTS

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Annotation: This thesis studies the effectiveness of interactive teaching methods and gamification approaches in developing technical thinking in students. In today's digital education process, the need to use innovative methods to form technological thinking and creativity among students is increasing. The study covers the theoretical and practical foundations of interactive teaching methods, including role-playing games, problem-based learning, collaborative learning and gamification methods. It also analyzes the role of gamification elements that serve to consolidate students' knowledge and develop their technological thinking skills. The approaches presented in the thesis reveal opportunities to increase students' interest and develop their independent skills in solving technical problems.

Keywords: technical thinking, interactive teaching methods, gamification, innovative education, role-playing games, problem-based learning, collaborative learning, technological thinking, students, modern education.

Introduction

Today's demand is that in the age of technology and innovation, the development of human thinking, especially the formation of technical thinking, is becoming increasingly important. For students, technical thinking is a key tool not only in the field of engineering, technology or exact sciences, but also in everyday life, in analyzing problems and finding solutions. However, in the modern educational process, dry theoretical knowledge often does not provide sufficient effectiveness in developing students' thinking. To solve this problem, the introduction of interactive methods and the use of gamification elements in the educational process is becoming an urgent issue.

Interactive teaching methods involve students in the process of active learning, improve their thinking skills, and form creative and critical approaches. Through methods such as role-playing games, group projects, and solving problem situations, students not only acquire knowledge, but also acquire skills for its practical application. Especially in an educational process enriched with digital tools and technologies, gamification methods - by introducing game principles into teaching - create favorable opportunities for

increasing students' interest and motivation, and developing their technological thinking.

Technical thinking is the ability to analyze problems and engineering tasks, think systematically and develop effective solutions. It is through an interactive approach and gamification that students become ready to strengthen their thinking, apply technological knowledge in practice, and create creative innovations. This thesis analyzes effective approaches to the development of technical thinking and reveals the role and importance of interactive methods and gamification in education. This is a solid step towards educating the future generation as the foundation of technological progress.

Methodology

The success of any scientific research depends on the correctness of the chosen methodology. In this work, modern pedagogical research methods were used to determine the effectiveness of interactive teaching methods and gamification elements in the development of technical thinking. The methodological foundations of the study were selected as a systematic approach, experiment, analysis and synthesis, and comparison methods.

Through a systematic approach, the essence of technical thinking and the process of its formation in students were extensively studied. In planning this process, the formation of technological skills, the integration of interactive methods into the educational process, and the identification of the stages of the gamification approach were primarily taken into account. In this regard, criteria were developed to measure the active participation of students in the learning process, the ability to solve technical problems, and the level of creative thinking.

Using the experimental method, which is the practical part of the study, the effectiveness of interactive teaching methods and gamification approaches was tested. Control and experimental groups consisting of students studying in the direction of technological education were formed as participants in the study. The experimental group used interactive methods such as role-playing games, problem-based learning, and collaborative project creation, and gamification methods enriched with game elements. The control group continued the traditional teaching method. The results analyzed the differences between the two groups and determined the effectiveness of the interactive approach and gamification methods.

Also, during the study, students' motivation, technological thinking indicators, and self-control skills were assessed using diagnostic tests,

questionnaires, and observation methods. The data collected using analysis and synthesis methods were summarized, and the advantages of interactive methods in developing technical thinking were identified.

During the study, approaches such as gamification-based tasks, project development, and group activities were considered as the most effective methods for developing students' technological thinking skills. These methods made it possible to make the educational process interesting, effective, and memorable by combining game and creative elements.

This methodological approach, as a result, served as a guiding basis for the formation of technical thinking, relying not only on theoretical but also on practical experience. The data obtained can be recognized as a significant contribution to the modern education system, creating the basis for the development of new methods for the effective transfer of technical knowledge.

Discussion

The issue of developing technical thinking in the modern educational process occupies an important place, since today's society requires young specialists who are deeply versed in technology, creative and critical thinkers. The results of the experiment conducted within the framework of this study on the effectiveness of interactive teaching methods and gamification approaches showed that, compared with traditional teaching methods, innovative methods significantly increase student activity. At the same time, students' interest, the level of independent mastery of knowledge, and creative thinking skills have qualitatively improved.

During the lessons in the experimental group, interactive methods such as role-playing games, problem solving, and collaborative project creation were used. These methods allowed students to actively participate in the lesson process and consolidate knowledge through real-life situations. In particular, when solving technical problems, students exchanged ideas and developed teamwork skills. In this process, it was clearly demonstrated that technological thinking is formed not only through knowledge, but also through the combination of analytical and creative approaches.

The use of gamification elements brought a new spirit and motivation to the lesson process. Game-based tasks, scoring systems, achievements, and ratings aroused interest in students along with a competitive spirit. As a result, they conducted creative research to solve technological tasks and developed the skills of not being afraid of difficulties, but striving to find solutions. This proves the effectiveness of game elements in developing students' technical thinking.

In the control group, when traditional teaching methods were used, students remained more passive observers, and there was no significant increase in their ability to independently analyze problems. This situation shows that for the development of complex and practical skills such as technical thinking, not only theoretical knowledge is not enough, but interactive and gamification-based approaches are needed, which are associated with active participation and practice.

Another important aspect was revealed during the discussion: interactive methods and gamification make the educational process interesting and effective, but they require a high level of methodological preparation and a creative approach from the teacher. Therefore, training teachers to effectively use these methods should be one of the priority areas of the education system.

In conclusion, we can say that interactive teaching and gamification have proven their effectiveness in the process of developing technical thinking. These methods teach students to think independently, solve technological problems with a creative approach, and work in a team. The widespread use of innovative approaches in preparing the future generation, especially motivational methods such as gamification, serves as one of the main factors of technological progress.

Conclusion

The development of technical thinking in the modern education system is considered one of the urgent tasks of today. The results identified during the study showed that interactive teaching methods and gamification approaches not only make the educational process more effective, but also teach students to take a creative and analytical approach to solving technological problems. These methods increase students' motivation, activate the educational process, and have a positive effect on the formation of technical thinking.

Through interactive methods, students have the opportunity to independently express their thoughts, communicate with each other, work in teams, and analyze problems from different perspectives. In this case, role-playing games, problem-based learning, and project approaches develop students' thinking by linking them to real-life situations. Gamification, by introducing game elements into education, arouses students' interest, increases their desire to compete and self-develop.

The results show that while traditional teaching methods in most cases are aimed only at imparting knowledge, interactive and gamification-based methods change students' attitude towards learning. They learn to apply knowledge in practice along with mastering it. This serves as an important basis for the

development of technical thinking. The role of such innovative methods in training competitive personnel in the age of technology is invaluable.

In conclusion, interactive teaching and gamification in the development of technical thinking are not only effective approaches, but also necessary parts of modern education. These methods allow students to be formed not only as recipients of knowledge, but also as creators and innovators. The future educational process should be based on cooperation between teachers and students, active participation and interest. Only then will the technical thinking of young people be strengthened and their place in a technological society be ensured.

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